

ADVANCED DEGRADATION MODELLING OF PHOTOVOLTAIC MODULES AND MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT: The recently started Austrian R&D project “ADVANCE! - Advanced Degradation Modelling of Photovoltaic Modules and Materials!”, a collaboration of Austrian applied science research and a module manufacturer, addresses innovative and complex statistical and data processing methods to enhance analysis and modelling of climate related degradation processes of photovoltaic modules. As a starting point, data from a previous project, that dealt with module design adaption to different outdoor climatic conditions, will be used, and enhanced by additional data derived from measurements and observations. In the first step the focus is on applying data science approaches on PV module stress testing results to achieve insight in underlying PV module degradation processes and to support manufacturing. An example for applying mixed effects modelling on power degradation data from 6-cell mini modules by means of pairwise comparison of aging actions using a base action, and one with an additional stress, is given, resulting in relative degradation values. Beside investigations on mini modules with identical BOM and different aging actions applied, variations in modules BOM are also investigated. In the next steps feature extraction from data will be continued and network structural equation models implemented. Of course, outdoor data analysis is necessary too, to understand module and system performance.

Keywords: PV-modules, stress testing and ageing, degradation modes, modelling.

1 AIM AND APPROACH

Due to the large effort in terms of time and equipment necessary for reliability testing of PV modules, the PV community has always endeavoured to obtain service life estimates, based on an extrapolation of measurement and characterization data from accelerated aging tests or modelling.

Thus, a recently started Austrian R&D activity (“Advance! - Advanced Degradation Modelling of Photovoltaic Modules and Materials!”) addresses innovative and complex statistical and machine learning data processing methods for digital analysis and improved modelling of the time and stress-dependent performance (degradation & reliability) of PV modules.

2 PROJECT OBJECTIVES

A wide variety of modelling approaches (statistical, chemical-physical-electrical) are developed and applied in order to identify interrelations between

- (i) the performance decline of operating PV modules
- (ii) the specific degradation behaviour of the materials and material composites used
- (iii) the stress conditions applied.

These interrelations will be used for innovative material and component development and the definition of predictive maintenance specifications. Figure 1 gives a schematic overview.

Figure 1: Schematics of the ADVANCE! project objectives.

This highly interdisciplinary research project is intended to open up new paths in the digital analysis of the long-term and degradation behaviour of PV modules and to lay the foundations for future highly efficient material developments for PV and predictive maintenance requirements for PV systems. Scientific innovation and relevance.

3 DATA BASE STRUCTURE, DATA TREATMENT

3.1 Test specimen and aging actions test schemes

Within the former Austrian flagship project INFINITY (2015-2018), [1] hundreds of framed mini modules with front glass and backsheets, including 6 monocrystalline cells each, were produced. One batch of such modules was with identical bill of materials (BOM), using an EVA encapsulant and a PET based backsheet, the other with varying BOM, with two backsheet types (CPO

and PPF) and three encapsulants (EVA, POE, TPO), respectively.

The “Aging Actions” and names are inspired by the Koeppen-Geiger climate zones [2], see Table I, and [1], now extended by calculated effective module surface humidity values.

Table I: Combined and sequential aging actions applied.

Aging action	Duration	Temperature T		Rel. Humidity H		Irradiance I	DML	Salt	TC	Intervals
		Module	Chamber	Module	Chamber					
Reference	1000h	1	85°C	85%	85%	-	-	-	-	constant
Moderate1	1000h	1	113°C	85°C	30,4%	85%	1000 W/m²	-	-	constant
Moderate2	1000h	1	78 °C	60°C	18,1%	40%	1000 W/m²	-	-	48h
		2	85°C	85%	85%	-	-	-	-	96h
Moderate3	1000h	1	78°C	60°C	18,1%	40%	1000 W/m²	-	-	48h
		2	85°C	85%	85%	-	-	-	-	96h
		3	-	-	-	-	-	1000 c	-	-
Moderate4	1000h	1	78°C	60°C	18,1%	40%	1000 W/m²	-	-	48h
		2	85°C	85%	85%	-	-	-	-	96h
		3	60°C	-	-	-	-	Salt-mist	-	-
Moderate5	3000h	1	78°C	60°C	18,1%	40%	1000 W/m²	-	-	48h
		2	85°C	85%	85%	-	-	-	-	96h
		3	-40/+85°	-	-	-	-	-	-	50 c
Alpine	2000h	1	85°C	85%	85%	-	-	-	-	250h
		2	113°C	85°C	24,9%	85%	1200 W/m²	-	-	-
Tropical1	3000h	1	-	-	85%	-	-	1000 c	-	24h
		2	85°C	85%	85%	-	-	-	-	constant
Tropical2	3000h	1	90°C	90%	50%	-	-	-	-	constant
Arid	1000h	1	128°C	95°C	15,7%	50%	1200 W/m²	-	-	constant

These values in column six were calculated for the modules surface under irradiation during damp-heat chamber conditions by means of measured surface temperature, water-saturation pressure and dew point [3].

Combined and cyclic stresses were applied to 6-cell mini modules, with three of them, in parallel, a “module group”, always to increase statistical reliability. In between tests, a wide variety of measurements was used: electrical I-V-curve measurement at STC and parameter extraction, (polymere) molecule spectroscopic and color index measurements as well as different imaging techniques like UV fluorescence (UVF) and electroluminescence (EL).

3.2 Data base

All measurement results were organized in an optimized database, which forms the information base for setting up models for climate sensitive aging and degradation processes. The database, using SQLite in conjunction with peewee [4, 5], was structured around the modules (DUT), which were logically connected via their specific aging module group with strictly associated aging actions and instances, Figure 2. Data triples for the three modules treated in parallel were logically grouped in the database with the corresponding measurement results.

Figure 2: Example for the database structure

Cumulated exposure-hours were calculated as time in climate chamber (h) × rel. humidity H (%), irradiance I (W/m²) and temperature T (°C), respectively. The three graphs in Figure 3 give the cumulated stresses applied during the different ageing actions, summarized in Table I.

Figure 3: Cumulated exposition hours for aging actions.

4 FIRST RESULTS

4.1 Modelling power degradation under varied stress input, identical module BOM

For having a basic stress applied (Aging action 1) and an additional stress in another aging action (Aging action 2) with the other parameters unchanged, and identical module BOM, pairwise comparisons, classical statistical mixed effects modelling [7] can be applied to the artificial ageing of modules with identical BOM, here an EVA encapsulant and a PET based backsheets. Changes in normalized MPP Power at STC (P_{MPP}) were fitted by means of model equation (1) using a ramp for the initial power gain, and an overlay of quadratic terms, one for the ageing action without, the other for the one introducing an additional stress, and an additional random term accounting for variation between similarly built and treated modules:

$$P_{MPP, norm}(t) = 1 + \beta_1 t \{t < 500h/3000h\} + \beta_2 t^2 + \beta_3 t^2 \{feature\} + b_{module} t^2 + e(t) \quad (1)$$

The fitted coefficients for the different aging action pairs (cf. Table I), are depicted in Table II.

Table II: Fitted mixed effects modelling coefficients for the modules P_{MPP} - pairwise comparisons.

Aging action 1	Aging action 2	Additional stress impact / feature	Coefficients			Coefficient ratio (β ₂ + β ₃) / β ₂
			β ₁	β ₂	β ₃	
Tropical 1	Moderate 1	irradiation	0.0257	-0.0431	-0.2588	7,0*
Moderate 1	Moderate 2	constant vs. sequential I	0.0292	-0.3320	0.1174	0.64*
Moderate 2	Moderate 3	DML	0.0278	-0.1955	-0.2754	2.41*
Moderate 2	Moderate 4	Salt mist	0.0249	-0.1566	0.0069	0.96
Moderate 2	Moderate 5	Temperature cycles	0.0207	-0.0103	-0.0315	4.06
Tropical 1	Tropical 2	Increase in T and H	0.0294	-0.0552	-0.0767	2.39*

The rightmost column gives a relative measure how much the additional stress forces degradation. The * indicates significant results applying a 95% confidence interval. In the following figures the time series of measured (left) and fitted (right hand side) P_{MPP} are compared:

Figure 4: “Tropical 1” (dashed lines) and “Moderate 1” (solid lines) P_{MPP} comparison. Left side measured, right side modeled, i.e. predicted power degradation.

Figure 5: “Tropical 1” (dashed lines) and “Tropical 2” (solid lines) P_{MPP} comparison. Left side measured, right side modeled, i.e. predicted power degradation.

In Figure 4 for the “Tropical 1” vs. “Moderate 1” (DH 85/85, additional feature 1000 W/m^2 irradiation), and in Figure 5 “Tropical 1” vs. “Tropical 2” (DH 85/85 \rightarrow DH 90/90) are compared.

4.2 Power degradation under identical stress, module BOM varied

Power degradation under DH stress was investigated for six different module types, having two backsheet variants (CPO and PPF) and three different encapsulants (EVA, POE, TPO). The measured (absolute) P_{MPP} for these six module types, represented by groups of three modules with identical BOM is compared in Figure 6, with a measurement interval of 1000 h.

Figure 6: Comparison of P_{MPP} measured, upper row CPO, lower PPF backsheets. Left side EVA, middle POE, right hand side TPO encapsulants. Aging action: up to 3000 h DH 85/85.

Changes in P_{MPP} and EL images are correlated to material degradation behaviour of the polymers.

Figure 7: UV-fluorescence images after 3000h DH 85/85. Upper row CPO, lower PPF backsheets, left side EVA, middle POE, right hand side TPO encapsulants.

Such changes are e.g. visible in the UV-fluorescence

images of the modules / encapsulants and UV-VIS-spectra [7, 8], given as an example in Figure 7 for the state after 3000 h DH 85/85.

5 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

Examples for investigations on mini modules tested by means of artificial aging actions, using combined and cyclic stresses and first evaluation and modelling steps for power degradation are explained. Data fits and modelling steps, applied to the existing measurement results, e.g. like the ones given as an example in chapter 4.1, and extracted values, e.g. shifts and intensity changes in molecule spectroscopy data will extend our data base.

For feature extraction from EL and UVF images (as depicted in chapter 4.2) deep learning-based image classification algorithms will be used, see [9], 5CV.2.11 in this EU PVSEC proceedings as well.

These data will then be used to generate mechanistic/inferential pathway models [10], by Network Structural Equation Models implemented in the statistical language R [11], netSEM package [12].

In addition to the data derived from artificial aging procedures, data from fielded PV systems, failure protocols, PV plant monitoring data and degradation rates will also be used [13,14] to compare with results from artificial aging, and therefore improve degradation modelling and forecasting.

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